

Supplementary Information

Cellulases and their promising use in tissue engineering and cell sheet technology

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In vitro simulation of wound healing using a scratch assay

The suitability of the material as a substrate for cell adhesion and growth, and thus for tissue engineering, is also demonstrated by its ability to promote the healing of wounds artificially created on its surface, i.e., by disrupting the continuity of the confluent cell layer on its surface by scratching. The bacterial nanocellulose modified by air drying and plasma treatment, i.e., BNC_AD_PM, appeared to be the most suitable substrate for confluent cell layer formation and cell sheet generation and was therefore selected for this experiment.

Sterile circular BNC_AD_PM samples were placed in a 24-well polystyrene plate and seeded with HaCaT keratinocytes at a density of 200,000 cells/well (approximately 106,000 cells/cm²) in 2 ml of DMEM medium supplemented with 15% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 40 µg/ml gentamicin, as described in the manuscript. The assay was performed on day 10 after seeding, when the cells had reached full confluence and their viability was 98%. The confluent cell layer was scratched manually with a sterile 10 µl pipette tip (**Figure S1 A**). Cell migration and proliferation leading to wound closure were monitored every 24 hours for 4 days. The relatively good transparency of the BNC membrane allowed us to obtain native images of the cells. The wound was well visible immediately after scratching the cell layer and was almost the same after the first 24 hours, although the edges of the wound were not as sharp as on day 0 (**Figure S1 B**). From day 2 onward, progressive wound closure was evident (**Figure S1 C**), and from day 3 to day 4, the wound was virtually closed with a continuous layer of cells (**Figure S1 D, E**).

Figure S1. *In vitro* scratch assay to analyze the wound healing properties of BNC_AD_PM. The wound in the confluent layer of HaCaT keratinocytes immediately after manual formation by scratching with a pipette tip (A), its appearance at 24 hours (B), and its gradual closure by migrating and proliferating keratinocytes from day 2 to day 4 after formation (C, D, E). Native images, Olympus IX 51 microscope, DP 70 digital camera, obj. 4×, scale bar 200 μm.

The next experiment was focused on the evaluation of the influence of cellulases on *in vitro*-simulated wound healing. First, a silicone insert (Ibidi, Germany, Cat. No. 80209) was firmly attached to the well bottom of a 24-well tissue culture polystyrene plate, and 50 μl of DMEM containing 106,000 cells/cm² was pipetted into each chamber of this insert (**Figure S2 A**). The cells were then allowed to grow to 100% confluence. The insert was then removed, revealing a continuous cell-free area at the 500 μm-wide divider of the insert, simulating a wound (**Figure S2 B**). The cell culture was then exposed to phosphate-buffered saline (PBS; pH 6.5) containing 37.5 units/ml of cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei*, i.e. the same concentration of cellulase used to separate cell sheets from BNC films. The cells were then incubated for 3 hours at 37°C in a humidified air atmosphere containing 5% CO₂, and then cultured in standard DMEM with 15% FBS and 40 μg/ml gentamicin. A cell culture with a cell-free zone without exposure to cellulase was used as a control sample. Five samples were used for each experimental group.

Figure S2. The insert and cell application for the scratch assay (A); wound width after insert removal (B).

<https://ibidi.com/culture-inserts/25-25-culture-inserts-2-well-for-self-insertion.html>

We found that *in vitro* wound healing was comparable in samples exposed and not exposed to cellulase and lasted only 2 days (**Figure S3**), suggesting that cellulase from

Trichoderma reesei does not interfere with the regenerative potential of cells. Similar results were obtained in a study by Hong et al. (2018), where the viability of human mesenchymal stem cells after 1 h exposure to cellulase concentrations ranging from 10 to 100 U/ml was not significantly different from that of unexposed cells [36].

However, our results obtained on polystyrene cannot be compared with those obtained on the BNC_AD_PM wound made with a 10 μ l pipette tip, which was much wider and therefore required more time to heal (up to 4 days). In addition, the method of wound creation using the silicone insert was not applicable to BNC_AD_PM due to its porous and fragile character.

Figure S3. Cell-free area in a confluent layer of HaCaT cells grown on polystyrene immediately after the removal of the silicone insert (day 0), and subsequent wound healing on days 1 and 2. **A-C:** control cells not exposed to cellulase, **D-E:** cells exposed to 37.5 U/mL cellulase for 3 hours (*). Olympus IX 51 microscope, DP 70 digital camera, obj. 4 \times , scale bar 200 μ m.